

Foundations of Systematic Management of Education Quality

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Abstract: This article defines the concepts of quality, quality of education, quality management of education, and also gives thoughts on the principles of system management and quality control of education in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: quality, quality of training, management of training quality, internal and external assessment, ensuring the quality of training.

In modern times, managing the education system is becoming increasingly complex. Educational institutions must operate in accordance with key demands for preparing skilled and competitive specialists in a rapidly developing society. Within and outside the education system, pedagogical and managerial innovations are emerging, creating opportunities for qualitative changes in methodologies and outcomes. These advancements make managing education quality more intricate, necessitating new, scientifically grounded approaches to address the challenges.

For instance, in his December 20, 2022, address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, "Improving education quality is the sole correct path for the development of a New Uzbekistan. We must continue our reforms in this field, interact more with educators, and collaboratively address issues they raise to enhance the quality of teaching and learning." Such directives place significant responsibility on educators across all levels of the education system.

Key policies, such as the June 5, 2018, Presidential Resolution No. PQ-3775 on "Additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms," and the June 21, 2022, Resolution No. PQ-289 on "Measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further develop higher educational institutions preparing pedagogical personnel," underscore the critical importance of addressing education quality as a pressing issue.

Global research on professional competence enhancement highlights a focus on the effectiveness of education management, prioritizing quality. Scientific studies in this field target the theoretical and methodological foundations of managing higher education, refining modern approaches to education quality monitoring, and ensuring harmony between quality and efficiency. This includes proposals for improving systems that assess the quality of higher education.

In Uzbekistan, educational reforms demand enhancements in content, planning, and management of education quality. This also involves developing mechanisms to improve

the professional competence and competitiveness of educators, ensuring the high quality of professional training.

The essence of managing education quality encompasses its socio-pedagogical and psychological aspects. Factors influencing quality improvement include the roles of government, society, institutional leadership, and the educational community in enhancing the processes of training and development. Significant research has been conducted on quality control, evaluation, and monitoring in education.

The Concept of Quality in Education

Managing education quality is a multifaceted challenge, spanning various levels (national, regional, institutional) and directions (organizational, structural, content-based, methodological, personnel-related, and resource-based). It integrates into the broader structure of education management, enhancing its effectiveness significantly.

Philosophical and Practical Understandings of Quality

Quality, as a concept, has evolved over time. Aristotle defined it as the distinguishing characteristics of objects, while 19th-century philosopher Hegel viewed quality as the intrinsic existence of an object, where losing its quality equates to losing its identity. Ancient Chinese thought connected quality to “balance” and “value,” suggesting its correlation with notions of excellence.

Modern interpretations, such as those by Shewhart (1931) and Ishikawa (1950), describe quality through objective and subjective lenses, linking it to consumer satisfaction and usability. Juran (1979) emphasized the need to align product quality with consumer demands, underlining its utility and satisfaction dimensions.

Education Quality

Education quality was first officially recognized in Uzbekistan’s normative documents in 1997, addressing state control over educational standards. It was defined as the comprehensive characteristic of professional understanding, aligned with modern developmental stages and economic demands. It signifies the ability of specialists to perform professional activities effectively and is tied to the capabilities and performance of individuals in their work.

Ensuring education quality requires continuous, systematic management by educational leaders, viewing governance as an ongoing, consistent process. Educational institutions, as dynamic social systems, must adopt methodological approaches that align with the general principles, laws, and functions of management to achieve effective outcomes.

Education Quality – A System for Achieving Predicted Outcomes

Education quality is a management system aimed at achieving predetermined results. It involves designing measures to ensure quality, motivating participants in the educational process for effective engagement, identifying deviations from objectives, observing and analyzing changes, and continuously improving all areas of institutional activity based on self-assessment.

Components of Education Quality Assessment

Education quality assessment consists of two components:

1. Internal Assessment (self-evaluation by the institution).
2. External Assessment (evaluation by external bodies or standards).

The mechanisms for these assessments may vary. External assessment is typically linked to standards and economic efficiency, while internal assessment focuses on improvements in

competitiveness and development. Globally, education quality assessment systems are often categorized into two conditional models based on their emphasis on internal or external evaluations:

1. **The French Model:** This relies on external assessment through accreditation, attestation, and control mechanisms to ensure institutional accountability to society and the state. In this model, self-assessment is given limited attention, as the primary focus is on effectively conducting external evaluations.
2. **The English Model:** This emphasizes internal assessment conducted by the institution itself.

Thus, education quality control involves both internal and external evaluations. These mechanisms differ, but internal assessment is shown to play a decisive role in ensuring education quality. Models based on quality assessment typically involve systematic self-evaluation, identifying strengths and weaknesses in the institution's performance, and addressing shortcomings to achieve continuous improvement.

Principles for Managing and Monitoring Education Quality in Higher Education Institutions

To effectively manage and control education quality in higher education institutions, the following principles should guide the process:

1. **Focus on Learners:** Prioritizing the needs of students.
2. **Leadership by Institutional Management:** Ensuring active leadership by administrators.
3. **Inclusive Staff Participation:** Broad engagement of institutional staff.
4. **Evidence-Based Decision-Making:** Making management decisions based on concrete evidence and conclusions.
5. **Systematic Approach to Management:** Utilizing a structured, system-oriented management approach.
6. **Continuous Quality Monitoring:** Maintaining ongoing oversight of quality.
7. **Alignment with International Standards:** Developing unified quality control indicators in accordance with global education quality standards.
8. **Performance-Based Evaluation:** Implementing evaluations based on key performance indicators (KPI) for faculty and administrative staff.
9. **Interactive Online Platforms:** Providing platforms for rapid communication between faculty, students, parents, and employers.
10. **Automated Feedback Systems:** Establishing automated systems for students to evaluate instructors immediately after classes.

The Need for Advanced Mechanisms

Managing education quality in higher education institutions requires improving mechanisms to enhance the professional competence of teaching staff. This approach should also promote democratic and humane principles of education governance.

Broader Implications of Education Quality Management

Education quality management ensures:

- Alignment of students' knowledge with international and national standards.
- Effective quality outcomes across various levels of education institutions.
- Successful institutional performance.

- Active participation of stakeholders in maintaining the quality of innovative educational services.

By emphasizing these principles, education quality management becomes a key driver of educational success, ensuring institutions adapt to modern demands while fostering continuous improvement in all areas of their operations.

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